

Research Paper

Quantifying Urban Expansion Pattern in Middle Ganga Plain using Remote Sensing and GIS techniques: A Case Study of Varanasi City, Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract

The satellite-based Earth observation technology can offer rich information of urban expansion by spatial quantification at regional and global levels. Thus, it can become the main approach to monitor urban expansion. *In this paper, we have extracted the spatial land information about urban expansion with the help of Average Urban Expansion Rate (AUER), Urban Expansion Intensity Index (UEII), and Urban Expansion Differentiation Index (UEDI) using six periods of Landsat images (1972, 1980, 1990, 2000, 2010 and 2020) and GIS technology. We have analyzed the rate, intensity, and spatial differentiation-based characteristics of natural urban land expansion of Varanasi city using the above-described method. The study results show that Varanasi city has expanded rapidly in its peri-urban area during the last 48 years. The highest AUER during this period was in the period 2000–2010, and the highest intensity was in the period 2010–2020. The spatial analysis shows that the natural expansion of the city is moving ahead in the North-West and South-West directions. The North-West and South-West regions are the hotspots for the expansion of Varanasi city, where people are increasingly settling down to meet their residential and commercial needs. Hence, rapid unplanned urban expansion is taking place in both these directions, which is an explicit challenge for the planning process in the study area that needs to be addressed.*

Keywords: Average Urban Expansion Rate, Urban Expansion Intensity Index, Urban Expansion Differentiation Index, Remote Sensing and GIS, Varanasi.

Introduction

The city or town of a geographical space is a permanent human habitation and the main center of their socio-economic activities. These urban areas offer better opportunities for people, their actions, and employment and business setups (kumar et al., 2011; Warlina & Damayanty, 2021). These urban areas attract the outside population quickly because they have a lot of facilities and services (Tian et al., 2017). As a result, its capacity to hold the growing population gradually decreases. So the growing population starts to settle in the peri urban areas to fulfill their commercial and residential needs (Rahman, et al., 2010). Thus, the naturally unplanned expansion of the city takes place that is directly linked to complex spatial, demographic, and socio-economic processes (Jedwab et al., 2017; Balk & Grace, 2019; Sarkar, 2020; Paul et al., 2021).

The increasing value of land due to changes in the pattern of land use in the peri-urban region of the city force people to move to lower-cost agricultural land (d'Amour et al., 2017). As a result, the process of land use change undergoes rapid changes, and the agricultural land in the peri-urban zone is swiftly converted to non-agricultural land (Fazal, S. (2000; Ifatimehin et al., 2006; Fanan et al., 2011; Martellozzo et al., 2015; Njiru, E. B. K., 2019). Such changes in land use patterns in peri-urban areas of the city are reflected as urban growth. It can be broadly classified into two processes - internal and external urban expansion. Both these processes of urban expansion create different and distinct spatial patterns. The external expansion is characterized by lateral physical growth or dispersion of built-up land, while the internal growth process emerges as compact development.

The phenomena of urban expansion is currently affecting developing countries more rapidly than the developed countries. Over the past decades, India has been experiencing a remarkable urban transformation (Mourya et al., 2021). The literary review suggests that the increasing growth of cities and urbanization have given rise to many problems, e.g. housing (King, et al., 2017; Adedire & Adegbile, 2018; Torquati et al., 2020), waste management (Kumar, et al., 2017; Malav, et al., 2020), water supply (Fazal, S., & Amin, A., 2011; Wakode, et al., 2018; Krueger, et al., 2019), social and health welfare, security, and traffic jams, etc. In India, large-scale migrations from rural and small urban areas resulted in a remarkable urban transformation into large cities (Bhagat, 2017; Zhou et al., 2019). As a result, these cities are experiencing unprecedented urban expansion and showing a tendency to grow at a faster rate (Lagakos, 2020).

It has been seen that many efforts are being made by the governments for a long time to achieve a sustainable urban area by controlling the unplanned urban expansion in the country (Parry et al., 2018; Raeisi, A., & Kiani, A., 2018; Aijaz, 2019; Mondal, 2021). Responsible government agencies are constantly striving to promote balanced development of geographic space to create new regional economic growth poles along with formulating urbanization policies (Adedire, 2018). Studies show that, the proposed land use in the study area, about 146 hectares has been affected by the land-use changes made by the government so far as per the Action Plan of Varanasi Master Plan 2011. On the contrary, about 969.50 hectares of land was unauthorizedly developed against the proposed land use in the master plan. It is clear that contrary to the prescribed land-use proposals, there has been unplanned development on a large scale, due to which many anomalies related to planning have arisen. To stop the unplanned and uncontrolled

development in the city and the adjoining outer areas of the city and to provide direction for future planned development, there is a need to pay adequate attention to the urban expansion taking place in the city along with its peri-urban area (Hermon, et al., 2018; Scott, 2019).

Keeping these limitations in mind, there are three main objectives of the present study. Firstly, the urban spatial information in the study area is to be extracted using satellite imagery. After that, a precise quantitative assessment of the spatial and temporal patterns of urban expansion in the study area is to be carried out using remote sensing data. Finally, to discuss the process and characteristics of urban expansion based on the obtained quantitative information and provide technical assistance and decision-making support for regional urban planning and development.

Study Area

Varanasi city (25°15'N to 25° 22' N and 82° 57' E to 83° 01' E) is a historical city situated on the left bank of river Ganges (Fig.1). It is one of the major cities of Purvanchal (Eastern Uttar Pradesh), and it is also a Mandal headquarter. It is situated on the Delhi-Kolkata National Highway No.-2, almost in the middle. New Delhi and Kolkata are located at a distance of 779 and 762 km from Varanasi city, respectively. It is connected to Jaunpur district (58 km) and Lucknow (300 km) by NH-56, to Chunar (45 km) and Mirzapur (78 km) by NH-7, and to Gazipur (81 km) and Gorakhpur (209 km) by NH-29.

Material and Methods

The objective of this research paper is to conduct a spatio-temporal study of the urban expansion of Varanasi city from 1972 to 2020 using built-up land data (Fig. 2) generated by supervised image classification. The whole methodology is shown in Fig. 3. In this process, the study area has been extracted by subsetting. After that, the obtained raw data is classified into built-up and non-built-up classes through the supervised classification method. The obtained built-up land data has been segregated and put to further use. Lastly, the Average Urban Expansion Rate (AUER), Urban Expansion Intensity Index (UEII), and Urban Expansion Differentiation Index (UEDI) have been chosen in this paper to reflect the spatial characteristics of the urban expansion of Varanasi city. Their details are as follows:

Average urban expansion rate (AUER) calculates the average rate of urban expansion in a given spatial unit between two time periods. This index indicates the rate at which built-up land has expanded within a defined boundary between the base year and final year (Acheampong et al., 2016). The calculation formula is as follows:

$$AUER_i = \left[\left(\frac{ULA_i^{t_2}}{ULA_i^{t_1}} \right)^{1/\Delta t} - 1 \right] \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where $AUER_i$ is the Average Urban Expansion Rate, $ULA_i^{t_2}$ and $ULA_i^{t_1}$ are the area of built-up land at the last and the base year, respectively, and Δt is the time gap in years.

The urban expansion intensity index (UEII) indicates the dimension of the change in the land area in the given time period. Thus, quantitative study of degree in urban expansion can be easily done by the spatio-temporal analysis of urban expansion intensity index. So we can define the UEII index as the ratio of newly developed built-up land in a spatial unit to the total area of that spatial unit. The formula is:

Fig. 3: Methodology of the Study

$$UEII_i = \left[\frac{ULA_i^{t_2} - ULA_i^{t_1}}{TLA_i \times \Delta t} \right] \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Where $UEII_i$ is the Urban Expansion Intensity Index for spatial unit. $ULA_i^{t_2}$ and $ULA_i^{t_1}$ is the urban area at the last and base years, respectively. TLA_i is the total area of spatial unit, and Δt is the time gap ($t_2 - t_1$) in years.

UEII Value	Characteristics
<0.28	Slow Expansion
0.28 to 0.59	Low-Speed Expansion
0.59 to 1.05	Medium Speed Expansion
0.05 to 1.92	Fast Expansion
>1.92	High Speed Expansion

Source: Acheampong et al., 2017.

UEDI quantifies the inequality of land expansion between different spatial units of an area, which can be made mutually comparable to those units. It is useful in identifying the hotspot of urban land change by evaluating the regional urban land expansion discrimination.

Thus, it is the ratio of the urban expansion rate of a spatial unit to the urban expansion rate of the whole study area. The calculating formula is:

$$UEDI_i = \frac{|UUA_i^{t2} - UUA_i^{t1}| * UUA_i^{t1}}{|UUA^{t2} - UUA^{t1}| * UUA_i^{t1}} \quad (3)$$

Here, UEDI is the Urban Expansion Differentiation Index of targeted spatial unit, and represents the area of built-up lands of that targeted spatial unit at the time and , respectively. and represents the total area of the study area at the time and , respectively.

Table 2: UEDI Characteristics and Its Range

UEDI Range	Characteristics
UEDI > 1	Fast Growing Area
UEDI = 1	Moderate Growing Area
UEDI < 1	Slow Growing Area

Source: Acheampong et al., 2017.

Analysis and Result

Average Urban expansion Rate in Study Area

Quantitative evaluation of the city concerned is of an utmost prerequisite subject in the entire process of town planning. This assessment can play an exclusive role in achieving the targeted infrastructure development goals for balanced and sustainable planning of the city. Varanasi is an ancient religious city that has undergone many spatial changes in the last 50 years, in which its urban expansion is significant. The present study shows that the average rate of urban expansion in study area during the period 1972-2020 was 3.38 per cent. Throughout the period, the highest rapid AUER was in the period 2000–2010, while the lowest AUER was in the period 1980–1990 (Fig. 4).

The AUER pattern at the spatial level indicates that the high AUER in the early period (1972-1980) was in the northern part of the study area. Later, in 1980-1990, the northern, north-western, south-eastern, and south-western parts were regions of high AUER. In the next two decades, only one part in each was the regions of high AUER, which was the south-eastern and northern parts respectively. Again, the AUER pattern changed later, and in 2010–2020 the north-west and south-western parts of the study area became areas of high AUER. Whereas the North-Western, Eastern, and South-Eastern parts in 1972–1980, the Eastern, Western, and Southern parts in 1980–1990, the Eastern part in 1990–2000, and the Eastern and Western parts in 2010–2020 were showing the lowest AUER. In the remaining parts, the AUER was moderate and low in different periods (Fig. 5).

Urban Expansion Intensity Pattern in Study Area

The Fig. 6 shows that the value of UEII was 0.44 during the entire period, i.e. the urban expansion in the study area has been grow at the rate of low-speed. The intensity of built-land expansion was lowest in 1980–1990, which was in the slow-development category. Likewise, the highest intensity of urban expansion was in 2010–2020, with moderate-speed development. The Fig. 6 shows that there has been a steady increase in the intensity of urban expansion after the period

1980-1990, i.e., there has been a steady increase in the intensity of the natural expansion of Varanasi city from 1990 to 2020.

Fig. 4: Temporal Pattern of AUER

Fig. 5: Spatial Pattern of AUER in Different Time-Periods

In addition to the above, the spatial pattern of UEII shows substantial variation. Fig. 7 shows that the intensity of urban expansion in different parts of the study area during 1972–1980 was characterized by low speed and slow development. Later on, the pattern of UEII shows the uniformity in the intensity of urban expansion in 1980–1990. It was the time when urban expansion in different parts of the study area was characterized by slow development. In 1990–2000, the urban expansion in the south-eastern part of Varanasi city increased faster than before, and built-up land developed here with moderate intensity; while the eastern and western parts were under slow development stage, and the rest of the remaining parts were in the moderate-

intensity stage of urban expansion. During 2000-2010, the urban expansion in the northern and south-eastern parts came to the high-speed development stage. In addition to these, urban expansions in the north-west, west, south-west, and south were in a medium-speed development stage. Apart from all the above, only the eastern part had been in a slow development stage of urban expansion. There was a further change in the intensity pattern of urban expansion by 2010-2020. In 2010-2020, the urban expansion in the north-west and south-western parts had entered in the high-speed development stage, i.e., the urban expansion intensity was highest in these two parts compared to the rest. Apart from these, the urban expansion intensity in the southern and south-eastern parts was going through a medium speed development stage. At the same time, north-eastern and south-eastern regions were at low-speed development stage of urban expansion intensity, and the northern and eastern regions were in the slow development stage of urban expansion intensity (Fig. 7).

Fig. 6: Temporal Pattern of Urban Expansion Intensity

Fig. 7: Spatial Pattern of Intensity of Urban Expansion

Fig. 8: Spatial Pattern of Urban Expansion Differentiation

Urban Expansion Differentiation in Different Parts of Study Area

UED is a useful index like AUER and UEII in the quantitative analysis of urban expansion, which shows the comparative analysis of built-up land expansion between different parts of the study area. Fig. 8 shows the differentiation patterns of urban expansion in different parts of the study area. In 1972–1980, the northern, north-eastern, southwestern, and western parts were fast-growing, while the northwestern, eastern, south-eastern, and southern regions were slow-growing areas in terms of urban expansion. The northern, north-west, south-east, and south-west were the faster-growing areas of urban expansion in the 1980–1990, while the north-eastern, eastern, and western parts were the slow-growing areas. The spatial differentiation pattern of urban expansion changed over in the 1990–2000. The northern, north-eastern, south-eastern, and southern parts in this period were fast-growing areas for urban expansion. In contrast, the north-western, western, south-western, and eastern parts were slow-growing areas. Similarly, the northern, western, and southeastern parts were fast-growing areas for urban expansion than the rest of the region in the period 2000–2010. The UEDI pattern changed again in 2010–2020, and the north-west and south-western parts of the study area became fast-growing areas for urban expansion. Apart from this, the southern part was moderate-growing, and the remaining parts were slow-growing areas for urban expansion (Fig. 8).

Findings

GIS-based analysis shows that Varanasi city has expanded at the rate of 3.38 per cent in the last 48 years. During this period, the intensity of its urban expansion has been low-speed development (0.44 per cent). It was observed in the study that after the period 1972-1980, there was a sharp fall in the natural expansion of Varanasi city. During this, the AUER declined from 4.43 per cent to just 0.83 per cent in 1980-1990. At this time, the intensity of urban expansion also decreased

from 0.26 per cent to 0.06 per cent. It is distinguishable from Fig. 4 and 5 that the period 1980-1990 was that time when Varanasi city had the least expansion. At this time, both the rate and intensity of urban expansion were at their lowest. The underdeveloped infrastructure outside the city limits and the housing attitude of the people was the main reason for this.

After 1980-1990, the rate of urban expansion increased sharply from 0.83 per cent (in period 1980-1990) to 4.97 per cent (in period 2000-2010), which was the highest rate in the entire study period. The rate of urban expansion followed this at 3.68 per cent in the period 2010-2020, with slight decreases. Likewise, the pattern of UEII continued to increase from 1980-1990 to 2010-2020. Urban expansion intensity shows the slow development stage in 1980-1990, now which shows the medium speed development stage in the period 2010-2020 with increasing growth. The main reason behind this was the rapid influx of people into Varanasi city and its peri-urban areas, who have come here from the surrounding countryside and small towns in different periods. The spatial analysis of urban expansion shows that the maximum growth of built-up land in the study area is in the northern, north-western, and south-western parts. The main reason for urban expansion in the northern and north-western parts has been the development of major connectivity routes like Shivpur Road, Shivpur Bypass, Panchkoshi Marg, Katoria Road, Sarnath Road and Nawalpur Road etc. along NH-58. NH-58 also connects Varanasi city to Lal Bahadur Shastri International Airport at Babatpur, which is another major factor for built-up land expansion in these parts. Due to the development of connectivity routes, people are increasingly attracted to the low-cost land available on the outskirts of the city's northern, north-western and north-eastern parts to meet their residential and occupational needs, which is another primary reason for unplanned built-up land expansion. Like the above, the main reason for expanding built-up land in the South-Western, Southern, and South-Eastern parts has been the Banaras Hindu University (BHU), Banaras Locomotive Works (BLW), and Lahartara and Chandpur Industrial Areas in these parts. Apart from these, the Vishwasundari bypass passing through the southern part has been the other primary reason where the establishment of new educational institutions as well as industries is the main reason.

The intensity analysis shows that there has been a substantial spatial change in the intensity of urban expansion in all the remaining parts except the eastern part of Varanasi city. The reason for the intensity of the built-land expansion in the eastern part is the river Ganges which has limited the urban expansion in these parts. Presently the intensity of built-up land expansion is highest in the North-West and South-West parts. The reason for these is also the same as above. The hotspot analysis of urban expansion shows that how the hotspots of the urban expansion had changed over time. Presently, the major hotspots of urban expansion are the north-west, and the south-west. These are fast-growing areas of urban expansion where built-up land is being expanded rapidly. Apart from this, the southern part is a moderate type growing area, where the built-up land is expanding rapidly with moderate pace.

Conclusion

It is observed in the present study that Varanasi city is witnessing uncontrolled expansion in its peri-urban areas, especially in the areas of Trans-Varuna regions and South Western and Southern parts. These parts are the first choice of people for residential and commercial needs. Presently Varanasi city is expanding rapidly towards north-west and south-west. It was found that

the kind of expansion pattern of Varanasi city, if it continues like this, can have many effects in future. Prominent among these impacts are infrastructural strains, housing and land availability, environmental degradation, traffic congestion and air pollution, urban heat island impact, water and sanitation problems, social disparities, loss of agricultural lands, and cultural heritage preservation. The effect of these reasons is gradually increasing in the study area. These causes are interconnected and often reinforce each other. The combination of economic opportunities, population growth, infrastructure development, and the presence of educational and industrial institutions have contributed to the expansion of Varanasi City over time. However, as with any rapidly growing urban area, there might also be challenges related to managing urban sprawl, ensuring sustainable development, and preserving the city's historical and cultural heritage. Effective urban planning and governance are crucial to address these issues and ensure the city's sustainable growth. Therefore, to achieve balanced and problem-free development in Varanasi city, some potential alternatives can be prominently included in the works of city planning in the city and its peri-urban areas. These potential alternatives are smart growth and urban planning, urban growth boundaries, transit-oriented development, revitalization of existing old areas, affordable housing and slum upgradation, green infrastructure and open spaces, strengthening peri-urban areas, strengthening community engagement and participation, and effective land use regulations and enforcement. So quantitative analysis of this unplanned urban expansion of Varanasi city has been the objective of the present study, along with highlighting the utility of GIS in quantifying urban expansion. At last, it is suggested that GIS-based spatio-temporal studies need to be harmonizing with factors affecting urban expansion, such as the demographic and socio-economic elements of the area, with an emphasis on developing more accurate and scientific study methods. Only then this type of study will be more useful and planning oriented.

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